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**ACADEMIC STRESS AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION IN RELATION TO
MENTAL HEALTH OF SIGHTED AND VISUALLY IMPAIRED STUDENTS
OF SENIOR SECONDARY
SCHOOL**

Education

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Abstract

Present study was undertaken to the academic stress and academic achievement motivation in relation to mental health of sighted and visual impaired students of senior secondary school. For this investigation, descriptive study was conducted, for this purpose 260 (130 visually impaired & 130 sighted) respondent of class 11th or 12th were selected randomly from two govt. blind and two govt. sighted schools. Sinha, Sharma and Nagpal's scale for measuring academic stress was used to see the magnitude of stress, Dr. T.R.Sharma's test for measuring academic achievement motivation was used to see the magnitude of motivation and Jagdish & Srivastava's Inventory was used to see mental health of the students. Investigator found that there is no significant relationship between academic stress, academic achievement motivation and mental health of visually impaired and sighted students.

Keywords: *Academic Stress, Academic Achievement Motivation, Mental Health, Sighted students, Visually Impaired Students.*

Introduction

Stress is common phenomenon of every life. It plays a crucial role in human life because all of us experience stress in different way. A person who suffers from stress may not be able to devote his full energy in the performance of a task. Stress interferes with the activity leading to impediment in learning. In termed as academic achievement motivation, motivation means stimulate internal instincts or inspires the person and its impact on academic achievement in termed as academic achievement motivation. Mental health takes us to lead a happy and well- contended life. It helps us in keeping balance between our needs and the capacity to meet these needs. It persuades us to change our ways of life according to the demands of the situation.

CONCEPT OF ACEDAMIC STRESS

Stress is a word derived from Latin word *Stringere*, meaning to draw tight, and was used in the seventeenth century to describe hardship and affliction Academic stress is mental and emotional pressure, tension, or stress that occurs due to the demands of school/college life. Some academic stress is normal for all school/college students, because of the stress that comes from being exposed to new educational concepts, adjusting to new social settings, and taking on the larger workload. Too much academic stress can contribute to depression and physical illness which can affect negatively to academic performance. Academic stress is mental and emotional pressure, tension or stress that occurs due to the demands of school/college life. Academic stress can contribute to depression and physical illness which affect negatively to academic performance.

It includes following dimensions.

- Cognitive
- Affective
- Physical
- Social/Interpersonal
- Motivational

ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION:

Academic achievement motivation is of paramount importance. In the school, real emphasis is

placed an achievement right from the beginning of formal education. The concept was first defined by Murray as the need, "If overcome and as quickly as possible".

The school has its systematical hierarchy based an achievement and performance rather than as creation or quality. The effectiveness of any educational system is gauged to the extent, the pupils involved in the system achieve, whether it be cognitive, affective or psychomotor domain. In general terms, achievement refers to the scholastic or academic achievement of students at the end of an educational programme. Motivation means stimulate internal instincts or inspires the person and its impact on academic achievement in termed as academic achievement motivation.

CONCEPT OF MENTAL HEALTH

The expression Mental Health consists of two words: Mental and Health. The 'Mental' generally means something more than purely cerebral functioning of a person. 'Health' generally means sound condition or will being of freedom from disease. Mental Health therefore means a sound mental condition or state of psychological well being and freedom from mental diseases.

Mental health has been defined as a positive sense of well being- physical, mental, social and not merely an absence of illness. Mental health is an integral component of total health; it is not merely an absence of mental illness. Thus, mental health is a balance between all aspects of life likes emotional, economical, and spiritual as well as physical which shows how we feel and think about our self, others and how we face life's situations. It is a balance between all aspects of life likes emotional, economical, and spiritual as well as physical which shows how we feel and think about our self, others and how we face life's situations. It includes following dimensions.

- Positive self evaluation
- Perception of reality
- Integration of personality.
- Autonomy.
- Group oriented attitude.
- Environmental competence.

Visually impaired students

Visually impaired children are those who satisfy one of the following conditions.

- (i) Total absence of sight
- (ii) Visual acuity not exceeding 6/60 or 20/200 (snellen) in the better eyes with correcting lenses.
- (iii) Whose field of vision is narrowed so that the widest diameter of his visual field extends an angular distance no longer than degree?

Sighted Students

The person whose visual acuity or vision is 6/6 or 20/200 and who can read without seeing problem is termed as sighted person.

JUSTIFICATION OF THE STUDY

Students with special needs may have a feeling of insecurity because of their various psycho-social and physical factors including causalities such as blindness, hearing impairment any other type of disability. Review of literature reveals that the number of psycho-social factors influence mental health level of school students e.g. behaviour school status, anxiety, popularity etc. It is further seen that relationship between mental health, academic stress and academic achievement motivation has not been studied satisfactorily. Therefore, investigator has decided to study academic stress and academic achievement motivation as a correlation of mental health.

As mention earlier visual impairment may affect psycho-social dimension including mental health and academic stress and academic achievement motivation with reference to student with visually impaired students. It would be interesting to find out whether sighted and visually impaired students differ significantly in terms of mental health and academic stress and academic achievement motivation level. This study will be helpful in better understanding of such students. Keeping these facts in mind, investigator has decided to plan and conducted the present study.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

1. To study the relationship between mental health and academic stress of sighted and visually impaired students.
2. To investigate the relationship between Mental Health and Academic Achievement Motivation of sighted and visually impaired students.

HYPOTHESES

1. There will be no significant relationship between the total academic stress and total mental health of visually impaired and sighted students.
2. There will be no significant relationship between total academic achievement motivation and total mental health of visually impaired and sighted students.
3. There will be no significant relationship between academic stress, academic achievement motivation and mental health of visually impaired and sighted students.

Review of Related Literature

Manisha and Sethi (2010) conducted a study of Mental health of adolescents in relation to academic stress. In these study 200 adolescents students were selected. There is no significant difference in the mental health of male and female adolescent's students. There are no significant differences in the academic stress of male and female adolescents. No relationship was found between the mental health and academic stress of male and female adolescents.

Sugutha and Matesan (2011) were conducted a study on academic stress and academic problems of adolescents of 500 girls. There is a positive correlation between stress and academic problems, which is statistically significant at 0.01 levels. That was when stress increase, the academic problem also increase that shown that the correlation between stress and academic problems is positive and high.

Muola (2010) conducted a study of the relationship between academic achievement motivation and home environment among standard eight pupils. The study was carried out on 235 students and their age ranged between 13 and 17 year. The findings of the study have indicated a positive relationship between academic achievement motivation and home environment. Home environment is on of the determinants of academic achievement motivation.

Ramachandran, Saraswathi and Rao (2011) investigate the impact of Religion, cast, income and type of family of the mental health of adolescents. In this study the sample of 120 adolescents in Junior college students. The result revealed that:

- Adolescents from Hindu families are better in their mental health than the adolescents from non Hindu families.
- Adolescents belong to forward cast are better in their mental health than the adolescents of backward cast.
- Adolescents from high income group better in their mental health than the adolescents from low income group.

There is no significant difference between adolescents from joint and nuclear families.

PLAN AND PROCEDURE

Sample

SCHOOL WISE DISTRIBUTION OF VISUALLY IMPAIRED STUDENTS

Sr. No.	Name of the School	Medium	No. of Students
1.	Institute for the Blind Chandigarh.	Hindi	65
2.	Govt. School for Blind Panipat	Hindi	65

SCHOOL WISE DISTRIBUTION OF SIGHTED STUDENTS

Sr. No.	Name of the School	Medium	No. of Students
1.	Govt. Model Sr. Sec. School, Chandigarh Sec. 26	Hindi	65
2.	Govt. Sr. Sec. School Panipat	Hindi	65

Collection of Data

In the case of sighted students, they read the questions and recorded the responses of the students in response sheet. In the case of Blind students, Investigator personally read the questions and recorded the response of the students in a response sheet.

TOOLS USED

1. Academic stress scale developed by Uday K. Sinha, Vibha Sharma, Mahendra K. Nepal.
2. Academic Achievement Motivation Test developed by Dr. T.R. Sharma.
3. Mental Health Inventory developed by Jagdish and Srivastava.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table-1

CORRELATION BETWEEN TOTAL ACADEMIC STRESS AND TOTAL MENTAL HEALTH OF SIGHTED AND VISUALLY IMPAIRED STUDENTS

Sr.	Variables	N	R	df	Significant
1.	Academic Stress	260	-.345	258	Significant at 0.01 level
2.	Mental Health	260			

Table-1 revealed that the coefficient of correlation between the scores of Academic Stress and Mental Health of Students (Visually Impaired and Sighted Students) was $-.345$, which was negative, but significantly high than the table value of coefficient of correlation 0.148 at 0.01 level of significant. Therefore, it can be concluded that there exists significant correlation between Academic Stress and Mental Health of Students. Hence, Hypothesis 1, which states "There will be not significant relation between Academic Stress and Mental Health of Sighted and Visually Impaired Students", is rejected.

Table-2

CORRELATION BETWEEN TOTAL ACADEMIC MOTIVATION AND TOTAL MENTAL HEALTH OF SIGHTED AND VISUALLY IMPAIRED STUDENTS

Sr.	Variables	N	R	Df	Significant
1.	Academic Achievement Motivation	260	.298	258	Significant at 0.01 level
2.	Mental Health	260			

Table-2 reveals that coefficient between the scores of Academic Achievement Motivation and Mental Health of Students (Visually Impaired and Sighted Students) is .298, which is positive but significantly high than the table value of coefficient of correlation 0.148 at 0.01 level of significance. Therefore, it can be concluded that there exists significant correlation between academic achievement motivation and mental health of students. Hence, Hypothesis 2 which states "There will be no significant relationships between the mental health and academic achievement motivation", is rejected.

Table-3

CORRELATION BETWEEN ACADEMIC STRESS, ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION AND MENTAL HEALTH OF VISUALLY IMPAIRED STUDENTS

Variable	N	R	Df	Significant
Academic Stress V.I. & S.I.	130	.112	128	Not significant at 0.05 level
Academic Achievement Motivation V.I. & S.I.	130	-.005	128	Not significant at 0.05 level
Mental Health V.I. & S.I.	130	.16	128	Not significant at 0.05 level

Table-3 reveals that coefficient of correlation between the scores of Academic Stress of Visually Impaired (VI) and Sighted (SI) Students is .112, which is positive but significantly less than the table value of coefficient of correlation .159 at the level of 0.05 level of significant. Therefore, it

can be concluded that there was not significant correlation between Academic Stress of Sighted and Visually Impaired Students.

1. Table-3 reveals that the coefficient of correlation between scores of Academic Achievement Motivation of Sighted and Visually Impaired Students is -0.005 , which is negative but significantly less than the table value of coefficient of correlation $.159$ at 0.05 level of significant. Therefore, it can be concluded that there was not significant correlation between Academic Achievement Motivation of Sighted and Visually Impaired Students.
2. Table-3 reveals that coefficient correlation between the scores of Mental Health of Visually Impaired (VI) and Sighted (SI) Students is 0.16 , which is significantly less than the table values of coefficient of correlation 0.159 at 0.05 level of significant. Therefore, it can be concluded that there exists no significant relation between Mental Health of Sighted and Visually Impaired Students.

Hence, the Hypothesis 3, which states, there will be no significant relationship between Academic Stress, Academic Achievement Motivation and Mental Health of Sighted and Visually Impaired Students.

MAIN FINDINGS:

1. There was negative and significant correlation between total academic stress and Total Mental Health of visually impaired and sighted students.
2. There was significant correlation between total Mental Health of Visually Impaired and sighted students.
3. There was significant correlation between Academic Achievement Motivation and Mental Health of visually impaired and sighted students.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

The present study is undertaken to determine relationship between academic stress academic achievement motivation and mental health. The study also aims to find out the relationship between visually impaired and normal seeing students. The study has its implications for the teachers, administrators and parents; academic stress academic achievement motivation and mental health are

important factors in the development of individual. It is the most important duty of teachers and parents to develop excellent mental health in visually impaired and sighted children.

The study shows that there is negative relationship between academic stress academic achievement motivation and mental health of visually impaired and sighted students. It means efforts to reduce academic stress will contribute to the improvement in the mental health of the students and academic achievement motivation depends upon the mental health.

Study also reveals that visually impaired students have higher level of mental health and lower level of academic stress academic achievement motivation as compared to their sighted counterparts. Therefore, school administrator, parents and teacher should make special efforts to improve mental health of such students by providing them more congenial environment and opportunity of social interaction. It helps the students to deal with their academic stress. The mental health develops the better academic achievement motivation.

The level of Academic Stress among sighted students is more than visually impaired students. So, teacher should take steps to minimize academic stress through guidance and counseling of these students.

SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER STUDY

1. The study may be extended to a large sample to get the better results.
2. The present study is confined to only age group of 12-18 years. A similar study can be conducted on other children or adult also.
3. The study can be conducted simultaneously on students studying in special school and in integrated school or specifically integrated school.
4. Affect of family background and environment on Academic Stress Academic Achievement Motivation and Mental Health can be studied.
5. Replication of the study can be done by using other tools and techniques of academic stress, academic achievement motivation and mental health.

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